

Digital Solutions for Resilient and Regenerative Supply Chains

Violeta Damjanovic-Behrendt
(*vdb@greentwin.at*)
GreenTwin GmbH, Austria

Wernher Behrendt
(*wernher.behrendt@greentwin.at*)
GreenTwin GmbH, Austria

Abstract

Purpose: Global surface temperatures in 2024 have risen by $+1.63^{\circ}\text{C}$, surpassing the UN Agenda 2030 and Paris Agreement goal of $+1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. Despite rising temperatures, global coal production continues to grow, though the Net Zero by 2050 scenario requires a 90% reduction in coal use (IEA, 2022). This gap between climate targets and industrial trends underscores the need for digital solutions to make sustainability trade-offs visible, thus enabling the formation of resilient and regenerative supply chains.

Figure 1: ECMWF/C3S Data on the Global Surface Temperature Increase in 2024

Approach: Our approach is centred on the design and implementation of digital tools and services that boost supply chain circularity, resilience and sustainability. In today’s rapidly evolving industrial landscape, SMEs face increasing pressures from market disruptions, regulatory shifts, and environmental concerns.

Our solutions aim to empower SMEs by providing them with tools to navigate these challenges effectively. Our recent innovative solution is a collaborative B2B cloud platform designed to support SMEs across various industries, including the digital sector (technology providers, technology innovators and consultancies). The platform is backed by the European Commission’s Collaborative and Support Action (CSA) project ResC4EU (Resilient Supply Chain for Europe), and is available free of charge to SMEs: <https://resc4eu.greentwin.app/>

By fostering collaboration knowledge sharing, and strategic partnerships, our platform helps SMEs build resilient, regenerative, and sustainable supply chains while maintaining a competitive edge. Modern supply chains must balance critical trade-offs to ensure their viability. Hence, our approach focuses on the following four Supply Chain (SC) dimensions:

- SC resilience, as a company’s capacity to navigate challenges, withstand disruptions, adapt, innovate and emerge stronger.
- SC regeneration that requires a commitment to conduct business in harmony with society and the environment, promoting circular economy principles and responsible sourcing.
- SC sustainability ensuring that industrial activities align with environmental and political goals set in Green Deal, by advocating resource efficiency, energy conservation and energy reduction.
- By contrast, the traditional economic models of SCs often prioritizes cost efficiency while ignoring negative impacts as “externalities”, e.g. environmental degradation and social impact.

Findings: Table 1 defines determining features for the design of platform services for supply chains.

Table 1: Features of Resilient, Regenerative and Sustainable SCs

	SC Resilience	SC Regeneration	SC Sustainability	Traditional SCs
Focus	Adaptability to changing conditions	Restoring natural habitats and resources	Resource efficiency	Cost efficiency
Processes	Adopting backup processes/sources	Circular economy practices	Optimized use of materials & energy	Enhanced revenue and profit
Suppliers	Alternative suppliers; Alternative processes	Regional sourcing, fair labour practices	Sustainable sourcing	SC optimization

Methods	Transparency and collaboration; Coordinated responses to risks, vulnerabilities and disruptions	Innovating for social & ecological regeneration	Transparency and sustainability reporting for stakeholders	Optimized inventory management; Reduced operational costs
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Practical Implications: Building resilient, regenerative, and sustainable supply chains requires not only innovative tools but also a strategic approach to overcoming real-world challenges. Our platform (ResC4EU Platform) has been designed with a clear scope, as outlined in Table 1, to support SMEs in navigating the complexities of modern supply chains:

- Resilient SCs: Enable SMEs to identify alternative suppliers, processes, and resources, ensuring adaptability to disruptions.
- Regenerative SCs: Prioritize regional sourcing, circular economy principles and fair labour practices, to enhance economic and social sustainability.
- Sustainable SCs: Encourage responsible sourcing and emissions reduction, ensuring compliance with evolving environmental and corporate sustainability regulations.

However, to fully optimize the platform's capabilities and empower SMEs, we must address key challenges that hinder resilience, regeneration, and sustainability:

- **Regulatory Compliance:** SMEs need structured guidance to align with sustainability standards such as the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) (CSRD, 2024), which will impact SMEs starting January 2027.
- **Advanced Collaboration:** Limited opportunities for new partnerships often restrict SMEs' ability to diversify supply networks. Hence, our AI-powered matchmaking system and collaborative knowledge hub facilitate connections with relevant technology providers, suppliers, and innovators.
- **Mitigating Supply Chain Disruptions:** We aim to integrate real-time risk assessment and predictive analytics using Copernicus Earth Observation data to provide SMEs with early warning systems and adaptive strategies.
- **Reducing product variety and quality trade-offs:** Sustainable and regenerative supply chains are expected to cause reduced product variety or quality due to sourcing constraints. We aim to boost alternative material sourcing, and shared production capabilities to maintain product diversity and quality while addressing sustainability goals.

Relevance/ Contribution: Modern supply chain platforms designed to enhance sustainability, resilience, and circularity are essential in addressing the unsustainable resource consumption that threatens long-term economic and social stability. To navigate today's complex landscape of supply chain disruptions, SMEs need digital tools that empower them to:

- Comply with the current and evolving regulations that mandate sustainable practices.
- Prove their resilience, regenerative capacity, and sustainability performance to regulators and stakeholders.
- Support sustainable business models to gain access to new markets, partnerships and funding opportunities,
- Ensure operational continuity and stability by adopting novel strategies.

Collaborative B2B platforms are leading the way towards resilience, regeneration, and sustainability in SCs, by fostering network that increase SME participation, enhance the flow of data and insight sharing, accelerate innovation and enable new adaptive SC models.

Keywords: Resilience, Sustainability, Supply Chain Trade-offs, Digital Platforms, B2B Platforms, Supply Chain Platforms

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References

IEA (2022), “Coal in Net Zero Transition”. IEA Report. Online available from: <https://www.iea.org/reports/coal-in-net-zero-transitions> (Latest access: 23 October 2024)

ResC4EU Platform (2024). ResC4EU Platform: <https://resc4eu.greentwin.app/>

CSRD (2024) Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD): <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022L2464>